

Supplementary material 3

Summary of descriptive statistics. Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES)

Items (question Q)	Statement: <i>I am able to...</i>	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Standard deviation
Commitment					
Q22	Consensus on classroom rules	4	9	7.00	1.24
Q4	Generate self-confidence	4	9	6.85	1.12
Q2	Promote critical thinking	3	9	6.80	1.17
Q14	Set up appropriate challenges	4	9	6.79	1.17
Q9	Formulate good questions	2	9	6.72	1.09
Q12	Advocating my teaching approach	3	9	6.57	1.25
Q6	Establish consistent classroom routines	3	9	6.49	1.23
Q1	Attending to struggling students	2	9	5.93	1.31
Instructional Practices					
Q17	Attending to specific needs	3	9	6.86	1.30
Q18	Establish clear expectations	2	9	6.86	1.34
Q10	Encourage creativity	3	9	6.60	1.29
Q11	Attending to diversity	3	9	6.32	1.24
Q7	Valuing learning	3	9	6.28	1.17
Q20	Calming disruptive students	2	9	5.94	1.40
Q23	Neutralizing problem behaviours	2	9	5.61	1.32
Q24	Engaging defiant students	2	9	5.52	1.30
Classroom Management					
Q13	Offer alternative explanations	4	9	7.17	1.23
Q19	Demonstrate academic responsibility	2	9	7.09	1.29
Q16	Diversify assessment	4	9	6.78	1.20
Q15	Implement innovative strategies	4	9	6.77	1.28
Q29	Self-evaluate my class	4	9	6.73	1.26
Q8	Perceive students' level of comprehension	2	9	6.65	1.15
Q25	Support families	4	9	6.62	1.33
Q27	Use non-aversive strategies	2	9	6.54	1.53
Q30	Manage classroom climate	3	9	6.32	1.23
Q3	Engage unmotivated students	3	9	6.22	1.22
Q5	Answer tough questions	2	9	6.31	1.51
Q26	Regain students' attention	3	9	6.00	1.21
Q21	Redress disruptive behaviours	2	8	5.56	1.25
Q28	Deal with unexpected behaviours	2	9	5.77	1.50

Note. The table shows the item values for the questions (Q) for each dimension, extracted from the Teachers' Sense of Efficacy Scale (TSES). Values are presented in descending order. Answers were given on a scale from 1 to 9 (highest value). Source: own elaboration.